

AN EXAMINATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONSTRAINT TO NIGERIA'S QUEST FOR A UNITED NATIONS SECURITY COUNCIL SEAT IN THE AFTERMATH OF THE COLD WAR.

Dr. Ponsah Saleh and Dr. Rabi Nimlan

Department of History and International Studies, University of Jos

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20121854>

Keywords

Structural Realism, Realism, and Permanent Five.

Abstract: *This article argues that the nature of international politics is structured in a manner that allows powerful states to determine outcomes within international organizations. It further noted that these powerful states are represented in the exclusive club of Permanent members of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC), including the United States of America, France, Britain, China, and Russia. The authors observed that these powerful states would resist any attempt to reduce their privileges by way of reform. Apart from their reluctance to reform, the article noted that they have set up stringent conditions that make it difficult for the Charter of the United Nations to be amended to pave the way for any meaningful reform of the UNSC. The article benefited from key informant interviews conducted in Abuja and Lagos and secondary data sourced from the Library of the National Institute for Policy and Strategic Studies, Kuru. To make meaning of the sourced data, the authors adopted realism theory and the micro-variant of structural realism to analyze the data.*

Introduction

In this age of guided missiles, constitutional amendment is pretty cumbersome. It is even more challenging when it involves big power

politics.¹ The above couplets were the opening remark of a 1958 article published in a journal of law², referring to the heavy challenges that confronted the early plan to review the Charter

¹ Zacher, Mark W. "The conundrums of international power sharing: the politics of Security Council reform." In *The United Nations and global security*, pp. 211-225. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US, 2004.

² Schwelb, E. (1958). Charter Review and Charter Amendment—Recent Developments. *International & Comparative Law Quarterly*, 7(2), 303-333.

Dr. Ponsah Saleh and Dr. Rabi Nimlan,

of the United Nations scheduled for 1955, exactly ten years after the United Nations came into being.³

But no matter how old the observation of Schwelb appears, many contemporary observers of international politics of the United Nations Security Council reform still maintain that some of the most visible challenges confronting the reform of the Security Council lies within its very founding charter and the reluctance of the permanent five members, namely United States, United Kingdom, Russia, China and France, to participate in a process that will potentially dilute or share their privileges.

Following from the observation above, this article argues that one of the major challenges that may hinder Nigeria's quest of securing a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council (UNSC)⁴ is the international challenge posed by charter article 108 and 109 on the one hand, and the unwillingness or resistance by the permanent Five (P5) to sanction a reform agenda that might tamper with the members' interest and further undermine their privileges. These analyses, as captured below, point to the obstacles that may hinder Nigeria's quest of securing a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council, since Nigeria's fate largely depends on the response of both the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA)⁵ and the

permanent members of the Security Council to the proposal for a charter review, which will in turn pave way for Security Council reform. But before we delve into the analysis proper, it is important that we first consider the underpinning theoretical framework that will help to provide greater insight into the subject under review.

Theoretical Framework

Any study of the United Nations and the privileges of the Permanent Five would have to embrace the central concept of the theory of realism, particularly its micro-variant of structural realism.⁶ Therefore, this article adopts realism as its central theoretical framework. This theory contends that states are preoccupied with the maintenance of power dynamics and are almost always hesitant in allowing their privileges to be diluted. Realism is an International Relations (IR) theory that views states as the main actors in an anarchic international system devoid of a superior authority. This anarchic political setting incentivizes states to engage in competition with others for survival. Therefore, the distribution of power among states dictates their behavior, causing a perpetual struggle for security, power, and dominance.

While defensive realists, such as Kenneth Waltz, argue that states seek an adequate amount of

³ Simma, Bruno, Daniel-Erasmus Khan, Georg Nolte, and Andreas Paulus. *The Charter of the United Nations: a commentary*. Oxford University Press, 2024.

⁴ Going forward, the United Nations Security Council will briefly be referred to as UNSC.

⁵ Henceforth, United Nations General Assembly can shortly be referred to as the UNGA.

⁶ Envisioned by Kenneths Waltz, Structural realism has since assumed prominence as a major theoretical framework for the studies of behavior of the Permanent Five and their refusal to reform the UNSC.

power for security, offensive realists, such as John Mearsheimer, maintain that states aim to maximize power to achieve hegemony, not for domination but as a way of self-preservation.⁷ In a self-serving system of political anarchy, states are attentive to relative gains, as they fear that others may gain more power from cooperation and threaten their security and survival. The lack of a world government to enforce rules when non-compliance occurs exacerbates this insecurity, invoking uncertainty and fear because every state can possess varying capabilities to harm one another. Since states cannot be sure of each other's intentions, war becomes a constant possibility in the international system. Thus, states strive to increase their capabilities relative to others, which has implications for the nature of interstate relations, particularly cooperation versus competition. Mearsheimer underlines that the characteristic of global politics is persistently competitive, albeit with periods of cooperative state engagement. He rejects the idea that great powers are committed to perpetual peace and cooperation. The U.S.'s prolonged presence in Europe, even after the Cold War, represents this everlasting strategic interstate competition. In an environment of relentless great-power competition, offensive realists argue that states should gain as much

power as possible and bid for hegemony, where and when possible, to ensure survival.⁸

Following from the above, it is important to note that Kenneth Waltz's views on structural realism appear to be relevant to the subject matter under discussion. To make meaning of the theoretical position adopted for this paper, an analysis of the charter provisions and resistance of the Permanent Five will help to drive home the subject under investigation.

Charter Articles 108 and 109

The most crucial problem facing the reform of the United Nations Security Council is the veto power of the Permanent Five. This is because, for any reform that may favour Nigeria's quest for a security seat, such a reform "must be inscribed into the Charter of the United Nations."⁹ This implies that for any reform of the Security Council to be successful, the Permanent Five must give their consent and the charter must be reviewed. This informed historian Paul Kennedy, described the veto power as "the catch-22" of the charter reform. The founders of the United Nations allowed only two alternative paths in the event of revision of the United Nations Charter in order to give room for reform of the Security Council, as captured in Chapter XVIII: an amendment to article 108 measures and article 109, which provided for the convening of a General Review Conference. According to 108:

⁷ Grieco, J. M. (1988). Anarchy and the limits of cooperation: A realist critique of the newest liberal institutionalism. *International Organization*, 42(3), 485–507

⁸ Zangin, M., Arash Namazi, and Parviz Ahadi. "Theoretical Analyzing of the United Nations Reform: UNSC." *Mitanni Journal of Humanitarian Sciences* 4, no. 2 (2023): 152-158.

⁹ Ashoms, Delvan. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Jos, 12th February, 2026.

Irish International Journal of Law, Political Sciences and Administration

I. Int. J. L. Pol. Sci. Admin.

Volume: 10; Issue: 03,

May – June, 2026

ISSN: 2146– 3283

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/iijlpsa/index>

“Amendments to the present charter shall come into force for all members of the United Nations when they have been adopted by a vote of two thirds of the members of the General Assembly and ratified in accordance with their respective constitutional processes by two thirds of the members of the United Nations, including all permanent members of the Security Council.”¹⁰ The article laid down a strict and bureaucratic condition requiring the consent by voting of a two-thirds majority of the members of the United Nations and ratification of any proposal for amendment before any form of reform to the present structure would be successful. This stiff proposal aligns with the views of structural realists, who are not ready to dilute their power with other states. Furthermore, the article requires that any proposal to amend the Charter be ratified by “all the permanent members of the UNSC” before the proposed amendments are carried out.¹¹

The strict requirements of the unanimous agreement of the permanent members of the Security Council appears as the greatest challenge to the proposed amendment of the Charter of the United Nations, especially now that “China and Russia have successfully aligned to oppose any agenda proposing an amendment

to the Charter even if other Permanent Members agree to reform the Security Council because of their quest to prevent states that they are not comfortable with.”¹² This is worsened by China's overzealous desire to veto any proposal that will include Japan, its neighbour.¹³ This hopeless situation has now come to resemble a “Cold War” type debate within the Security Council, where members hardly agree on any substantive matter.¹⁴

The inflexible conditions for Security Council reform have continued to block any practical proposal for amendments to the United Nations Charter. As a matter of fact, during the organization's sixty-eight years of existence, there have been only three successful amendments to the charter with only a single amendment regarding the Security Council.¹⁵ This was in 1965 when resolution 1990 was approved by a two-thirds majority of the members of the United Nations General Assembly and unanimously adopted by the Security Council, thus expanding the Security Council from 11 to 15 members and increasing the majority required for a decision from seven to nine members. However, the approved amendment proposal did not tamper with the Permanent Members category or modify the

¹⁰ UN Charter Art. 108

¹¹ Akdağ, Yavuz. "REFORM STALEMATE ON THE UNITED NATIONS SECURITY COUNCIL." *Anadolu Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi* 27, no. 1 (2026): 102-119.

¹² Aisha, Manu. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 12th April, 2026.

¹³ Guzzardi, Jose E., and Mark J. Mullenbach. "The politics of seeking a permanent seat on the United Nations Security

Council: An analysis of the case of Japan." *Midsouth Political Science Review* 9 (2007): 35-73.

¹⁴ Druckman, Daniel, and Paul C. Stern, eds. *International conflict resolution after the Cold War*. National Academies Press, 2000.

¹⁵ Hosli, Madeleine O., and Thomas Dörfler. "Why is change so slow? Assessing prospects for United Nations Security Council reform." *Journal of Economic Policy Reform* 22, no. 1 (2019): 35-50.

Dr. Ponsah Saleh and Dr. Rabi Nimlan,

veto rights of the Permanent Five. The discouraging antecedent of the Amendment of the United Nations Charter made Thomas Weiss, an astute commentator on the UN reform debate, to conclude thus:

“The history of reform efforts geared towards making the security more reflective of growing UN membership and of changing world politics since the establishment of the organization conveys the slim prospect for meaningful change.”¹⁶

Article 109 is the second alternative to any meaningful UN Charter amendment, as contended in Chapter XVIII:

“A General Conference of the Members of the United Nations for the purpose of reviewing the present charter may be held at a date and place to be fixed by the two-thirds vote of the members of the General Assembly and by a vote of any nine members of the Security Council. Each member of the United Nations shall have one vote in the conference.”¹⁷

The foremost clause of Article 109, requiring a ‘General Conference of the members of the United Nations for the purpose of reviewing the present charter’ and the following subsection demanding approval of two-thirds of members of the Security Council, in all intent and purpose is similar to the strict conditions enshrined in Article 108. Basically, the Permanent Five's rights to veto any proposal aimed at amending the Charter of the United Nations assigned to

them in article 108 and 109 denotes that only one member of the Permanent Five who, for whatever interest, is empowered by the Charter to impede any proposed amendments to the Charter which seeks to enlarge or expand the permanent seat of the UNSC.

Justifying the need to maintain the status quo, scholars like Lund argue that an abolition of the veto may not serve well the goal of maintaining global peace and security well, which is the fundamental objective of the United Nations.¹⁸ Pushing further on this line of argument, they claim that the League of Nations has taught the world a bitter lesson, and with such a lesson in mind, it will be difficult to sustain the debate for the reform that seeks to reduce the privileges of the world's most powerful states.¹⁹ Though this line of argument may be getting historically out of date, if measured by atomic weapons, GDP, or population. After all, it was the US Congress's refusal to join the League of Nations, accompanied by other problems, which led to its collapse. This, according to the Permanent Five, would weaken the capacities of the strong powers toward contributing (financial and otherwise) to the organization. Based on the foregoing analysis, one can conclude that once the veto is erased or tampered with, the United Nations may come to resemble its predecessor organization.

There are those who, in their desperate efforts to support the maintenance of the status quo,

¹⁶ Weiss, Thomas G. "The illusion of UN Security Council reform." *Washington Quarterly* 26, no. 4 (2003): 147-161.

¹⁷ Article 109 of the UN Charter.

¹⁸ Lund, Jakob Silas. "Pros and cons of Security Council reform." *Center for UN Reform Education* 19 (2010).

¹⁹ Lund, J. S. (2010). Pros and cons of Security Council reform. *Center for UN Reform Education*, 19.

advanced what Beck called “apocalyptic arguments.”²⁰ The underlying assumption of this school of thought lies in its emphasis on the avoidance of any nuclear war; its appeal centers on the need to maintain the present structure in order to prevent nuclear war. Since all the Permanent Five possess large nuclear arsenals, the veto serves as a rallying point where their differences can be resolved diplomatically. Even though this particular argument can hardly be sustained, taking into cognizance the fact that there are other states, such as North Korea and Israel, that also possess nuclear capabilities yet are not members of the Security Council, it will not be easily dispelled because the great powers have always resorted to diplomacy when dissatisfied with one another's actions.

Drawing from the foregoing analysis of the requirements for the amendment of United Nations Charter, which is a precondition to any form of reform to the present structure of the Security Council, it can be easily understood that the inherent contradictions within the institutional framework limit the possibility of reform of the UNSC. In other words, it lessens the chances of member states such as Nigeria, whose quest is to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC. One can further argue, taking into cognizance China's present bitter support with the West and Russia's voting antecedent, that it is not only unlikely to reach a consensus among the Permanent Five but that the feasibility of a

substantive Security Council reform is unrealizable. In any event, reform of the Security Council is unlikely and unattainable, especially when the requirement of a two-thirds vote of the General Assembly and concurrent Permanent Five backing for review of the United Nations Charter. Therefore, a closer look at Nigeria's quest to secure a seat in the Security Council clearly illustrates a struggle in futility.

Resistance from the Permanent Five

One of the most challenging obstacles to Nigeria's quest for a permanent seat in the UNSC is the idea that states have always resolutely protected their own national interests.²¹ This notion (which is one of the major characteristics of state behavior in the international system) provides the rationale of states' determined pursuit of wealth and power, which is the ultimate guarantee of their survival and security through whatever means available.²² Like other states, this practice has always characterized the behavior of the permanent members of the Security Council. With this in mind, it will not only be difficult to break the logjam of the Security Council and alter its structure, but it may also render Nigeria's quest to secure a permanent seat unrealizable. This can easily be deduced from the logic of the concepts of realism, which perfectly explain the behavior of permanent members of the Security Council through a

²⁰ Beck, Ulrich. "War is peace: On post-national war." *Security Dialogue* 36, no. 1 (2005): 5-26.

²¹ Rice, Condoleezza. "Promoting the national interest." *Foreign Aff.* 79 (2000): 45.

²² Puchala, Donald J. "World hegemony and the United Nations." *International Studies Review* 7, no. 4 (2005): 571-584.

careful reading of the antecedent of the use of their veto.

This explanation of realism stems from a careful observation of the behavior of states—in this case, members of the Permanent Five—by scholars in the field of international relations who argue that in their struggle to project their national interest within the framework of the United Nations, they have developed and formed the kind of hierarchy of major powers and small powers.²³ This perspective further claims that the major powers, who in this case are permanent members of the United Nations, are determined to maintain their hegemonic statuses and have always sought to control the small powers, which include countries like Nigeria, which are down the ladder of economic development. The major powers govern the international system, not in the interest of small powers, but in their own interests.

This position appears very strong in the writing of Hans J. Morgenthau, when he concluded that: “Despite the profound changes which have occurred in the world, it still remains true, as it has always been true, that a nation, confronted by the hostile applications of other nations, has one prime obligation: to take care of its own interest.”²⁴

Stressing further on how states will always strive at all costs to protect their national interest—

what he referred to as *raison d'etat*—Morgenthau argued:

“Hence, the council that ought to subordinate our traditional interest to some other standard is unworthy of a nation's greatness in human civilization. A nation that will take the council and act consistently on it will commit suicide and become the prey and victim of other nations, which know how to take care of their interests.”²⁵

Drawing from the above line of reasoning, many policymakers and scholars who favored the maintenance of the status quo have not only criticized the call to reform the Security Council but have even gone further to openly justify the preservation of the status quo. To them, the structure of the Security Council, especially the permanent category, still reflects the leading political, economic, and military powers. This point of view has always been anchored by the United States Council on Foreign Relations, which stated that “enlargement will dilute US power, increase gridlock, encourage lowest common denominator actions, and empower antagonistic leaders of the non-aligned movement.”²⁶

Could this adequately explain the failure of some attempts in the past to reform the body? Commentators on the theme of Security Council reform have offered various explanations for the failure of the past attempts, but the one most

²³ Lieven, Anatol, and John Hulsman. "Ethical realism and contemporary challenges." *American Foreign Policy Interests* 28, no. 6 (2006): 413-420.

²⁴ Morgenthau, Hans J. "The primacy of the national interest." *The American Scholar* (1949): 207-212. P. 210.

²⁵ Morgenthau, Hans J. "The primacy of the national interest." P. 211.

²⁶ McDonald, Kara C., and Stewart M. Patrick. *UN Security Council enlargement and US interests*. No. 59. Council on Foreign Relations, 2010.

compelling factor which relates to this paper seems to be the power struggle and resistance by the major powers who double as the Permanent Five to maintain their control, and in some instances, the struggle to increase their space within the organization as dictated by their national interest.

Furthermore, this same practice of defending their national interest has found expression in Beijing's behavior. In a well-written but defensive article published in 2005, Akinterinwa argues that even though democracy is one of the best systems of government and needs to be internationalized, the call in some quarters to democratize the Security Council falls under a different topic entirely.²⁷ Corroborating the position above, a senior staff member of the Nigeria Institute for International Affairs in Lagos opined that “the concept of permanent membership and that of democratization of International Relations belong to two different categories with no fundamental links between them; the topic of democratization of International Relations deserves full exploration on other occasions.”²⁸ A clear reading of China's recent reaction to the issue of Security Council reform suggests that Beijing will offer strong opposition to Japan and India's quest to secure a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council.²⁹ Even though

China has not explicitly opposed Nigeria's quest, they are in a position to veto any attempt at reform of the Security Council. Despite Beijing's close economic relationship with Japan and India, its political rapport with India, and especially Japan, is characterized by great animosity. It is not in the interest of China to see another Asian power becoming a member of the Security Council as an equal, argues Imoghe.³⁰ China has always seen the Security Council as a privilege that must be guarded closely. This, according to Wuthnow, may have informed her description of the Security Council in the 1960s as “a tool of big power hegemony.”³¹

But the desire to oppose the inclusion of traditional enemies of some of the permanent members in the quest to enlarge the Security Council is not limited to China. Washington has also demonstrated in various instances the urge to protect the national interest and prevent the inclusion of her traditional enemies in the permanent club. For instance, Washington has outrightly opposed the inclusion of Germany (her wartime enemy) and Brazil (from the same region as her). More worrisome is the hard fact that both China and the US have both played this kind of diplomatic tactics of supporting the rivals of their opponents; while the US is seen to be opposing China's own rivals (Japan and India), China is seen to be lending support to US

²⁷ Akinterinwa, Bola A. "Nigeria and the permanent membership of the United Nations Security Council: Dynamics and definienda." *Nigeria and the Development of African Union. (Nigeria: Vantage, 2005)* (2005): 35-86.

²⁸ Abolarin, Adetutu. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 19th March, 2026.

²⁹ Wu, Wencheng. "China's Position towards UN Security Council Reform: Balancing Legitimacy and Efficiency." *Strategic Analysis* 44, no. 5 (2020): 502-509.

³⁰ Imoghe, Inioma. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 26th March, 2026.

³¹ Wuthnow, Joel. *Chinese diplomacy and the UN Security Council: Beyond the veto*. Routledge, 2013.

rivals (Germany and Brazil). Similarly, it is very unlikely that the United Kingdom and France would willingly surrender the last vestiges of their great power status or even share it with new rivals.

This goes to show how China and America's desire to protect their national interests will have a profound effect on Nigeria's quest of securing a permanent seat in the Security Council. China or America may not be interested in hindering Nigeria's quest per se, but they may be forced by the desire to protect their national interest, which is to ensure that their enemies are prevented through the veto. If this kind of rivalry, which characterized China/US relations, degenerates, the quest to reform the United Nations in general will not be feasible, and Nigeria's quest of securing a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council in particular will not be realized.

Even among the permanent members, the United States' status overshadows the rest. The United States not only overshadows the rest but has always showcased a willingness to act separately when its national interest collides with that of the UN. For instance, US unilateralism, as exemplified in her invasion of Iraq and her recent threats to withdraw financial support to the UN over the General Assembly's consideration of the Palestinian State, shows that she can act apart in order to protect her

national interest; both policymakers and scholars acknowledge this fact. Nowhere has this been made clearer than in Weiss's widely cited article, when he stated that “the idea that the remaining superpower will continue to participate, politically or financially, in an institution whose purpose will be a power limit has no precedent.”³²

There is no clearer explanation of the above point of observation than in the US National Security Strategy released by President Bush:

“We created the United Nations Security Council so that, unlike the League of Nations, our deliberations would be more than talk. Our resolutions will be more than wishes... we will be prepared to act apart when our interests and unique responsibilities require.”

Conclusion

In conclusion, from the foregoing analysis, it is evident that Nigeria's quest will be consumed by the resistance of the Permanent Members of the Security Council. These exclusive club would be compelled by their desire to protect their national interest and prevent any reform that seeks to upset their positions. These and other factors, such as the strict conditions for the review of the United Nations Charter, which is a prerequisite to the reform of the Security Council, only constitute a serious constraint to Nigeria's quest of securing a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council.

³² Weiss, Thomas G. "The illusion of UN Security Council reform." *Washington Quarterly* 26, no. 4 (2003): 147-161.

References

Secondary Sources

Akdağ, Yavuz. "REFORM STALEMATE ON THE UNITED NATIONS SECURITY COUNCIL." *Anadolu Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi* 27, no. 1 (2026): 102-119.

Akinterinwa, Bola A. "Nigeria and the permanent membership of the United Nations Security Council: Dynamics and definienda." *Nigeria and the Development of African Union. (Nigeria: Vantage, 2005)* (2005): 35-86.

Beck, Ulrich. "War is peace: On post-national war." *Security Dialogue* 36, no. 1 (2005): 5-26.

STERN, PAUL C., and DANIEL DRUCKMAN. "Conceptual Challenges." *International Conflict Resolution after the Cold War* (2000).

Grieco, Joseph M. "Anarchy and the limits of cooperation: a realist critique of the newest liberal institutionalism." *International organization* 42, no. 3 (1988): 485-507.

Guzzardi, Jose E., and Mark J. Mullenbach. "The politics of seeking a permanent seat on the United Nations Security Council: An analysis of the case of Japan." *Midsouth Political Science Review* 9 (2007): 35-73.

Hosli, Madeleine O., and Thomas Dörfler. "Why is change so slow? Assessing prospects for United Nations Security Council reform." *Journal of Economic Policy Reform* 22, no. 1 (2019): 35-50.

Lieven, Anatol, and John Hulsman. "Ethical realism and contemporary challenges." *American Foreign Policy Interests* 28, no. 6 (2006): 413-420.

Lund, Jakob Silas. "Pros and cons of Security Council reform." *Center for UN Reform Education* 19 (2010).

McDonald, Kara C., and Stewart M. Patrick. *UN Security Council enlargement and US interests*. No. 59. Council on Foreign Relations, 2010.11. *Enlargement and US Interests*. No. 59. New York: Council on Foreign Relations.

Morgenthau, Hans J. "The primacy of the national interest." *The American Scholar* (1949): 207-212.

Puchala, Donald J. "World hegemony and the United Nations." *International Studies Review* 7, no. 4 (2005): 571-584.

Rice, Condoleezza. "Promoting the national interest." *Foreign Aff.* 79 (2000): 45.

Schwelb, Egon. "Charter Review and Charter Amendment—Recent Developments." *International &*

Irish International Journal of Law, Political Sciences and Administration

I. Int. J. L. Pol. Sci. Admin.

Volume: 10; Issue: 03,

May – June, 2026

ISSN: 2146– 3283

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/iijlpsa/index>

Comparative Law Quarterly 7, no. 2 (1958): 303-333.

Simma, Bruno, Daniel-Erasmus Khan, Georg Nolte, and Andreas Paulus. *The Charter of the United Nations: a commentary*. Oxford University Press, 2024.

Chapter, V. I. I. I., X. I. Chapter, Declaration Regarding Non-Self-Governing Territories, and X. V. I. Chapter. "Charter of the United Nations." *available at the website <http://www.UN.Org/en/documents/charter/chapter14.shtml> (accessed 2 March 2020)* (1945).

Weiss, Thomas G. "The illusion of UN Security Council reform." *Washington Quarterly* 26, no. 4 (2003): 147-161.

Primary Sources / Interviews

Abolarin, Adetutu. Interview with Ponsah Saleh. Abuja, March 19, 2026.

Aisha, Manu. Interview with Ponsah Saleh. Abuja, April 12, 2026.

Wu, Wencheng. "China's Position towards UN Security Council Reform: Balancing Legitimacy and Efficiency." *Strategic Analysis* 44, no. 5 (2020): 502-509.

Wuthnow, Joel. *Chinese diplomacy and the UN Security Council: Beyond the veto*. Routledge, 2013.

Zacher, Mark W. "The conundrums of international power sharing: the politics of Security Council reform." In *The United Nations and global security*, pp. 211-225. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US, 2004.

Zangin, M., Arash Namazi, and Parviz Ahadi. "Theoretical Analyzing of the United Nations Reform: UNSC." *Mitanni Journal of Humanitarian Sciences* 4, no. 2 (2023): 152-158.

Ashoms, Delvan. Interview with Ponsah Saleh. Jos, February 12, 2026.

Imoghe, Inioma. Interview with Ponsah Saleh. Abuja, March 26, 2026.